

Mesomorphic Characteristics of Binary Mixtures of Structurally Dissimilar Mesogens

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Binary mixtures, none, one or both components, of which are liquid crystals, have been studied in sufficient details over the years and the findings have been quite interesting and enlightening^{1,2}. Binary mixtures, both components of which are liquid crystals, are known to form continuous mixed liquid crystals¹. Most of them do not undergo any change in their mesomorphic textures³, though a few have been reported giving rise to different textures. We have reported a mixture where a higher order phase emerges from mixture of two nematogens³ and a lower order nematic phase emerges from mixture of a smectogen⁴ and non-mesogen⁵. Emergence of mesophase, increase or decrease of the mixed mesomorphic range⁵ and thermal stabilities and the study of the factors which influences the modifications have received more attention⁶. Earlier, we have reported binary mixtures of structurally similar mesogens and non-mesogens⁷. We report here three binary systems of structurally dissimilar mesogens to study the effect on mixed mesomorphism due to the difference in structural characteristics of the components. The binary mixtures are composed of an azodye (A), namely, 4-n-hexyloxy-phenylazo-4'-propiophenone and ester (B₁-B₃), viz. 4-nitrophenyl-4'-n-alkoxybenzoates. The components have general formula.

- A : HPAP $n = 5$, $Z = -N=N-$; $-\text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_3$
 B₁ : NPBB $n = 3$, $X = -\text{COO}-$; $-\text{NO}_2$
 B₂ : NPHB $n = 5$, $X = -\text{COO}-$; $-\text{NO}_2$
 B₃ : NPOB $n = 7$, $Z = -\text{COO}-$; $-\text{NO}_2$

The binary systems studied are : (1) HPAP + NPBB, (2) HPAP + NPHB and (3) HPAP + NPOB.

Results and Discussion

Binary system 1 : In this system (Fig. 1) it is seen that the monotropic nematic of B₁ changes to mixed enantiotropic nematic with the addition of as low as 10 mol% HPAP. The smectic A phase appears at about 30 mol% A and the phase length widens up at the cost of nematic phase. The phase diagram shows that the enantiotropic phase covers the composition range 10–48 mol% A, after which only

smectic phase predominates. This can be attributed to the fact that the terminal attractions are no longer sufficient to cause nematic orientations, as layered orientations become prominent. The K → M curve reaches the eutectic point at 50° at about 29 mol% A. Within the mixed mesophase region, the S-I curve is in smooth continuation with the N-I curve.

Fig. 1 Binary system 1 : (●) solid-mesophase, (○) smectic-nematic, (Δ) nematic-isotropic and (□) smectic-isotropic

Binary system 2 : In this system (Fig. 2), with the addition of about 10 mol% of smectogen A, the enantiotropic nematic phase appears, which continues upto about only 30 mol% A, after which only smectic A phase prevails. The mixed smectic and nematic mesophase region is exhibited from 20 to 30 mol% A. Eutectic point is obtained at 50° at about 30 mol% A. The early appearance of the smectic phase as compared to that in system-1, can be attributed to the addition of two methylene units in B₂ component which provides added lateral adhesions. It is observed that two methylene units make a difference of about 10 mol% in terms of bringing the magnitude of lateral adhesions to the level of being effective for smectic mesophase

to appear. In this system also, the S-I, N-I curves are in smooth continuation. The S-N curve merges with S-I and N-I curves on extrapolation.

Fig. 2 Binary system 2: (●) solid-mesophase, (○) smectic-nematic, (Δ) nematic-isotropic and (□) smectic-isotropic.

Binary system 3: This system (Fig. 3), consisting of component A and component B₃, is polymesomorph. As the concentration of component A increases in the mixture, it causes the K → M transition to depress successively to minimum 50° at about 32 mol% A. In this system, the mixed mixture smectic and nematic mesophase regions exist upto 32 mol% A, beyond which, on further addition of smectogen A, smectic phase predominates upto 100 mol% A.

We can summarise the salient features of the binary systems as follows. As the molecular geometry of the components in the mixture differ, we see that the S-N, S-I and N-I transition curves deviate from the linear nature. This rising tendency can be due to different moieties of the terminal groups and central bridges. Non-linear behaviour of binary phase diagrams, where one of the components has a strong polar end-group have been reported by various workers⁸. In this mixtures also, deviation from linearity rule, can be attributed to nitro groups, high tendency of favouring formation of oriented fluids. On account of this deviation, the maximum mesophase range turns out to be more than 55° in all the mixtures, which is quite a wide range. In systems 2 and 3; the polymesomorphic region does not extend beyond 30 mol% A, which indicates the predominance of highly smectogenic property of A. The mixture shows smectic A phase which can be characterised by the

Fig. 3. Binary system 3: (●) solid-mesophase, (○) smectic-nematic, (Δ) nematic-isotropic and (□) smectic-isotropic.

focal conic texture. The enhancement of the smectic phase in systems 2 and 3 can be due to the lateral attractive forces originating from the dipole moment of the keto group. Most of the textures show super cooling below 40°.

Experimental

4-Hydroxyphenylazo-4'-propiophenone was synthesised from acetanilide by reported methods⁹. 4-n-Hexyloxyphenylazo-4'-propiophenone was synthesised by alkylating the above propiophenone with n-hexyl bromide. 4-Nitrophenol-4'-alkoxybenzoates were synthesised from 4-n-hydroxybenzoic acids by reported methods¹⁰. The compounds were crystallised from alcohol and their elemental analyses were found satisfactory.

The components were weighed in known proportion and melted together in fusion tubes. The mixtures were thoroughly mixed in the melt to obtain homogenous mixtures. After cooling the solid obtained was finally ground and used for determining transition temperatures. The transition temperatures were determined by using a Leitz-Laborlux 12 POL microscope.

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References

1. A. D. BOGOTAULENSKY and W. WINGRADOW, *Phys. Chem.* 1907, **60**, 433; 1908, **64**, 229; R. WATIER, *Chem. Ber.* 1925, **58**, 2303.

NOTE

- J S DAVE and J M LOHAR, *Proc Nat Acad Sci India, Sect A*, 1960, **29**, 35, 1962, **32**, 105, J S DAVE and M J S DEWAR, *J Chem Soc*, 1955, 4616, 4305, J S DAVE and J M LOHAR, *Chem Ind (London)*, 1959, 597, *Indian J Chem*, 1966, **4**, 386, *J Chem Soc (A)*, 1967, 1473, J M LOHAR and G H PATEL, *Curr Sci*, 1975, **44**, "Liquid Crystals", ed S CHANDRASEKHAR, London, 1980 p 533
- 2 J M LOHAR and U MASHRU, "Liquid Crystals", ed S CHANDRASEKHAR, London, 1980, p 543, J M LOHAR and D S SHAH, *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst*, 1973, **28**, 293
- 3 J M LOHAR and JAYRANG S DAVE, *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst*, 1983, **103**
- 4 J S DAVE, P R PATEL and K L VASANTH, *Indian J Chem*, 1966, **4**, 505, *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst*, 1969, **8**, 93
- 5 C M PARMAR, JAYRANG S DAVE and K P DHAKE, *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst*, 1992, **213**, 51
- 6 R A VORA and R GUPTA, *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst*, **106**, I I YU and M M LABES, *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst*, 1979, **54**, 1, K P L MOODITHAYA and N V MADHUSUDHANA, "Liquid Crystals", ed S CHANDRASEKHAR, London 1980, p 297
- 7 JAYRANG S DAVE and K P DHAKE, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1991, **68**, 438
- 8 J P SCHROEDER and D C SCHROEDER *J Org Chem*, 1968 **33**, 591 J W PARK and M M LABES, *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst*, 1977, **34**, 147, C S OH, *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst*, 1977 **42**, 1, A C GRIF FIN and J F JOHNSON *J Am Chem Soc*, 1977 **99**, 4859
- 9 KUNCKFELL, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1943, 113
- 10 J M LOHAR and J S DAVE, *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst*, 1983, **103**, 143